

Novel Online Static Eccentricity Detection and Evaluation in Permanent Magnet Generators

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Abstract— Static eccentricity is a fault strongly related to the manufacturing process of electrical machines and the incorrect positioning of the rotor inside the stator. As such, it is important to develop reliable tests, aiming for the diagnosis and severity evaluation of this fault before the machine is sent to the customer. There have been issues with the detection of static eccentricity in induction motors online, especially in motors producing principal slot harmonics, while the most reliable tests have been offline ones. The area of static eccentricity detection in permanent magnet generators is yet lacking widely adopted diagnostic procedures of low complexity. In this work, the authors will evaluate most common methods for their capacity to detect the static eccentricity in direct drive permanent magnet generators, while under operation. While current methods will be shown to fail, the authors will propose a novel online method capable of producing reliable diagnostic outcomes.

Keywords— Permanent magnet machines, eccentricity, fault diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Direct-drive Permanent Magnet (PM) machines are key devices in remote renewables [1], such as offshore wind, tidal and wave energy harvesters. This is due to their capability to operate at low speed, while connected to the grid via a power converter. The absence of a gearbox is essential in such applications since it reduces the maintenance needs that are particularly high due to the difficult physical access of such generating systems [2].

Like other electrical machine types, PM generators may experience different faults such as eccentricity [3], demagnetization [4], stator inter-turn faults [5], mechanical faults [6] etc.

Eccentricity may be static or dynamic depending on whether the air-gap asymmetry is fixed in time or not. However, in most practical cases the two types tend to co-exist forming a condition known as mixed eccentricity. It is worth noting that the two eccentricity types have different origins. Among the various possible faults, static eccentricity is the one attributed to the assembly stages of the generators and is not typically created during operation. On the other hand, the dynamic eccentricity may be caused by a bent shaft or problems with the bearings and its degradation mechanism is related to the operation of the machine.

Many research efforts can be found in the literature regarding the static eccentricity detection in electrical machines [7]. It is noteworthy to say that this fault is static by nature and as such, poses several challenges for its online detection. In the field of induction motors for example, if the rotor slot number is an integer submultiple of the poles' number, the motor current signature analysis does not offer relevant signatures. Therefore, off-line methods have been proposed to solve such issues in both induction and synchronous machines [8]-[10]. A few works based on vibration analysis [11] and neural networks [12] can be found in the literature, aiming for static eccentricity detection. Furthermore, the flux monitoring has been proposed together with other methods [13]. Static eccentricity may be inclined and in the unbalanced magnetic pull caused by it has been studied as well [14]. Regarding fault identification, the authors of [15] have shown that it is not possible to misinterpret static eccentricity for broken rotor magnets when the stator current spectrum is studied for fault detection. Finally, the eccentricity will have a direct impact on the air-gap magnetic flux density distribution, thus directly affecting the coil currents and causing increased losses in some of them [16]. The pattern is different between dynamic and static eccentricity conditions.

In this work, the authors are focusing on the development of a reliable methodology for the detection of the static eccentricity fault in direct-drive permanent magnet generators. The specific features of the test subject are that it is a radial flux machine, consisting of a single stator and double rotor construction, it belongs to the family of C-GEN generators [17] and finally it is air-cored. The generator model has been developed using the Finite Element Method (FEM) and has been verified by experimental testing of a prototype. Then, static eccentricity is introduced in the model and most popular methods are evaluated as to their sensitivity or capability to detect the fault, such as the flux and stator current monitoring [18]. After determining their incapacity, a new methodology based on the zero-sequence flux has been developed. Moreover, an enhancement of the original solution is presented via the introduction of two magnetically coupled sensing coils. Through this work, the overall losses performance of the machine has been studied and the occurring Joule losses have been studied. The static eccentricity fault is shown to have a strong impact on the thermal degradation of the generator, especially when the stator has coils connected in parallel.

II. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The FEM model that has been developed for this research is shown in Fig. 1, together with the actual prototype. Moreover, the main generator characteristics, as well as the comparative operating parameters are shown in Tables I and II respectively, demonstrating the validity of the developed model. Minor differences are due to the pure resistive load feeding of the power produced by the generator in the simulation and inherent asymmetries that always exist in real devices but are absent in simulations. Despite those, the developed model describes the real device with reasonable accuracy.

a)

b)

Fig. 1. a) The developed FEM model and b) the actual generator.

TABLE I. GENERATOR CHARACTERISTICS

Rated power	21.5 kW
Rated speed	100 rpm
Stator	Coreless
Frequency	26.67 Hz
Pole pairs	16
Stator coils	24 x single concentrated
Stator coil turns	205
Magnet material	N42 recoil NdFeB

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE RESULTS

Variable	FEM	Experiment
Phase voltage (V)	300.74	306.7
Stator current (A)	17.18	17.41
Torque (Nm)	1567	1575
Output Power (kW)	15.5	15.4
Input Power (kW)	16.41	16.5

III. FAULT ANALYSIS

In this section, the authors will demonstrate the most critical findings. The generator is simulated to operate under different levels of static eccentricity (20%, 30% and 40%). The level of the static eccentricity in this case is measured as the displacement of the inner rotor with respect to the stator coils. This is because the magnetic airgap is not the same as the mechanical one. Moreover, the machine has one magnetic airgap but two mechanical airgaps.

In order to test the reliability of the most popular diagnostic methods, the authors have analysed the spectra of the stator current and the magnetic flux. The magnetic flux is captured by a coil sensor which is built inside a stator coil. The voltage of the sensor, which is proportional to the flux, is then analysed with the use of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The resulting spectra are shown in Fig. 2. The results are disappointing, while none of the two methods is capable of producing characteristic fault signatures. This is attributed to the double rotor feature which mirrors the asymmetry of the fault between the two machine sides, in conjunction with the lack of iron core to induce a spatial magnetic asymmetry.

a)

b)

Fig. 2. FFT of: a) the stator current and b) the flux, under healthy and faulty conditions, while the generator operates under rated load.

The inability to detect the fault with conventional methods is dangerous. The fault causes the existence of circulating currents in the stator coils. Some of the coils are seriously over-stressed while others are under-stressed. Obviously, the problem is for those that are over-stressed. The added current will lead to increased losses and elevation of their temperature, thus leading to faster degradation of the insulation and the higher probability of an early stator inter-turn or phase to phase fault. Fig. 3 demonstrates the current density in the middle of the stator coils along the stator circumference. The worst coil case has 42% higher current density under fault compared to the healthy condition. A better overview is shown in Fig. 4 depicting the spatial current density distribution in the machine under healthy and faulty conditions. This result is critical, since the machine's line current does not present any differences, however the machine is thermally overstressed.

Fig. 3. Current density in the middle of the stator coils along the circumference for the healthy (blue) and generator with 40% static eccentricity.

a)

b)

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of the current density on the: a) healthy and b) machine with 40% static eccentricity at steady state.

The uneven distribution of the current affects the stator coils that are connected in parallel, forcing them to carry circulating currents since the produced electromagnetic forces are uneven under fault. Such changes are shown in Fig. 5. In the machine the four parallel connected coils carry the exact same current, however the distribution changes when there is a fault, while the current difference increases with the increase of the fault severity. The respective current changes are summarized in Table III. Two of the coils are shown to carry higher current than the rated one, while the other two are undercharged. More specifically, the worst case (meaning the coil with the greatest current increase) has changed by 8.62%, 13.29% and 17.95% with respect to the three faulty cases. This automatically means an increase of the local Joule losses by 17.99%, 28.34% and 39.12% respectively.

Table IV depicts the electromechanical variables for all the cases. It is clear that the inner coil current imbalances do not impact the total generator current. Overall, there is a slight drop of the efficiency with the increase of the fault severity. From a diagnostic point of view, the line current is unaffected by the fault.

a)

Fig. 5. Currents of the four parallel coils at -90° (black), -45° (blue), 0° (red) and 45° (green) under: a) healthy, b) 20% static eccentricity, c) 30% static eccentricity and 40% static eccentricity condition.

TABLE III. PARALLEL STATOR COIL CURRENTS

Coil location	Healthy	20% SE	30% SE	40% SE
-90°	4.29 A	4.66 A	4.86 A	5.06 A
-45°	4.29 A	4.53 A	4.66 A	4.79 A
0°	4.29 A	4.19 A	4.15 A	4.10 A
45°	4.29 A	3.85 A	3.67 A	3.51 A

TABLE IV. OPERATING VARIABLES OF THE MACHINES

	Healthy	20% SE	30% SE	40% SE
Vrms (V)	300.7	300.7	300.7	300.7
Irms (A)	17.18	17.19	17.19	17.19
Pmech (kW)	16.409	16.423	16.439	16.461
Pel (kW)	15.505	15.506	15.506	15.506
Efficiency (%)	94.49	94.41	94.32	94.19

IV. FAULT DIAGNOSIS VIA THE ZSF

A solution to this fault detection problem is urgently sought. The authors propose the use of the zero-sequence flux (ZZF) as the diagnostic mean capable of producing static

eccentricity fault signatures while in operation. The reason that the ZZF is expected to succeed where both the stator current and the flux fail is due to its dependance on the third flux harmonic.

The rationale is that if three flux sensors are installed in the healthy stator at 120 electrical degrees apart, they will sense a flux density with a phase difference 120 degrees in time. The induced sensor voltages due to Faraday's law will be as in eq. 1. Therefore, when the three signals are added up over time, the harmonics of frequencies $(6k \pm 1)f_s$ will cancel out. Those are the harmonics observed in the stator current spectrum (1st, 5th, 7th etc.). On the other hand, the odd triplets will remain and therefore, the zero-sequence flux's fundamental will be at $3f_s$ (eq. 2).

On the other hand, if the machine suffers from static eccentricity, the non-uniform air-gap will lead to a non-uniform air-gap permeance and a different reluctance of the generator's magnetic circuit as a function of space. Now, the three flux sensors will not sense the same amounts of magnetic flux. When added up, the $(6k \pm 1)f_s$ will not cancel out and reveal the static eccentricity fault.

$$\begin{cases} V_a = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} V_n \cos(n\omega t) \\ \vdots \\ V_b = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} V_n \cos\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ \vdots \\ V_c = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} V_n \cos\left(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{zs} = V_a + V_b + V_c = \sum_{k=3(2m+1)}^{\infty} 3V_k \cos(k\omega t) \quad (2)$$

The analysis above is possible with two possible strategies. Firstly, the three flux sensors are placed 120 electrical degrees apart and secondly 120 mechanical degrees apart. Although in this application, both methods can be easily applied, in different machine types there may be applicability issues due to the external geometry of the tested machine, therefore one of the two may be implemented.

The frequency spectra of the zero-sequence flux, calculated with electrical angle difference of 120 degrees, are shown in Fig. 5 for all cases. The healthy machine has a relatively weak harmonic at 50 Hz (-48.41 dB) and one at 250 Hz (-62.95 dB). Those should not theoretically exist in the healthy machine but are present due to small asymmetries caused by the non-linear characteristic of the permanent magnets as well as inherent minor model asymmetries. Despite that, when the machine suffers from static eccentricity those harmonics increase in amplitude, while their increment is monotonic with that of the fault level severity (Fig. 6).

a)

b)

c)

d)

Fig. 5. Zero-sequence flux spectra of: a) healthy machine and faulty with b) 20%, c) 30% and d) 40% static eccentricity, calculated with sensors located at 120 electrical degrees apart.

Fig. 6. Amplitude difference of the 50 Hz and 250 Hz harmonics as a function of the fault severity level (electrical phase difference of 120 degrees).

Moreover, the frequency spectra of the zero-sequence flux, calculated with mechanical angle difference of 120 degrees, are shown in Fig. 7 for all cases. The healthy machine has a relatively weak harmonic at 50 Hz (-48.39 dB) and one at 250 Hz (-62.94 dB). Despite that, when the machine suffers from static eccentricity those harmonics significantly increase in amplitude, while their increment is monotonic with that of the fault level severity (Fig. 8). A comparison between Figs 5-8 reveals that the sensitivity of the method is enhanced when the three sensors are placed at 120 mechanical degrees apart from each other. This result is reasonable considering that in this case, the sensors sense a higher fault severity level, overall. However, it is to be noted that although weaker the methodology using the electrical phase difference can also have some success in identifying the fault.

a)

b)

Fig. 7. Zero-sequence flux spectra of: a) healthy machine and faulty with b) 20%, c) 30% and d) 40% static eccentricity, calculated with sensors located at 120 mechanical degrees apart.

Fig. 8. Amplitude difference of the 50 Hz and 250 Hz harmonics as a function of the fault severity level (mechanical phase difference of 120 degrees).

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